

First record of *Clogmia albipunctata* and *Atrichobrunettia (Mirousiella) graeca* (Diptera: Psychodidae) from Romania, with the updated checklist of non-Phlebotominae species

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Abstract: The rare European species *Atrichobrunettia (Mirousiella) graeca* Ježek et Goutner, 1993 and the invasive species *Clogmia albipunctata* (Williston, 1893) (both Diptera: Psychodidae) are newly recorded from “Dunele Marine de la Agigea” Nature Reserve from Romania. The updated checklist of non-Phlebotomine species of the family Psychodidae for Romania with 53 species is given.

Keywords: biodiversity, checklist, Europe, Maruinini, Mormiini, Palaearctic Region, Paramormiini, Pericomaini, Psychodinae, Psychodini, Sycoracinae, Trichomyiinae

Introduction

Psychodidae (Diptera: Nematocera) is a family of small hairy midges, known as “moth flies” and “sand flies”, with approximately 3000 described species worldwide (e.g. Pate et al., 2011; Curler & Moulton, 2012; Morelli & Biscaccianti, 2021). The sand flies (subfamily Phlebotominae) with nine species are well studied in Romania (e.g. Lupașco et al., 1965; Dancesco, 2008; Cazan et al., 2019a, b, 2021a, b.; Dvorak et al., 2020). The non-phlebotomine moth flies (subfamilies: Bruchomyiinae, Psychodinae, Sycoracinae, and Trichomyiinae) are not sufficiently researched in Romania.

Therefore, the main goal of this work is to publish new faunistic records and to summarise and re-

evaluate the checklist of non-Phlebotominae species of the family Psychodidae of Romania.

Material and methods

The material presented in this work was caught using a Malaise trap in Agigea (Constanța County, “Dunele Marine de la Agigea” Nature Reserve, 44°05'16.4"N 28°38'32.3"E, 13 m a.s.l. (locality – Fig. 1); Romania) by A.-M.P. The samples were stored in 96% ethanol and subsequently determined by J.O. using Ježek & Goutner (1993) and Ježek & van Harten (2009). The material is deposited in the ethanol collection in the Department of Ecology, Faculty of Humanities and Natural Sciences, University of Prešov, Slovakia.

Fig. 1. The “Dunele Marine de la Agigea” Nature Reserve – the location of Malaise trap used in the summer season in 2022 (recent photo: March 2023).

Results and discussion

Faunistic results

Family Psychodidae
Subfamily Psychodinae
Tribus Mormiini
Subtribus Brunettiina

Atrichobrunettia (Mirusiella) graeca Ježek et Goutner, 1993

Material examined: 1 ♂ (Fig. 2), 25.viii–6.ix.2022, Malaise trap, A.-M.P. leg, J.O. det.

Rare species known only from Greece, Albania, Czech Republic, Great Britain, Ireland (*angustipennis* sensu Withers, 1989) (Ježek & Goutner, 1993; Ježek, 2003; Ježek & Omelková, 2012). First record for Romania.

Tribus Paramormiini
Subtribus Paramormiina

Clogmia albipunctata (Williston, 1893)

Material examined: 1 ♂ (Fig. 3), 6–13.ix.2022, Malaise trap, A.-M.P. leg, J.O. det. Expansive, often synanthropic, circumtropical and circumsubtropical species (e.g. Ježek & Goutner, 1995; Oboňa & Ježek, 2012; Humala & Polevoi, 2015; Afzan & Belqat, 2016; Bejarano & Estrada, 2016; Cazorla-Perfetti & Moreno, 2017; Ježek et al., 2018; Cazorla-Perfetti, 2019; Oboňa et al., 2019, 2021; Salmela et al., 2019; Zित्रा et al., 2020; Morelli & Biscaccianti, 2021; Jaume-Schinkel et al., 2022; Martynov et al., 2022). Its occurrence in Romania has not yet been published. First record for Romania.

With the exception of epidemiologically interesting species from the subfamily Phlebotominae (e.g.

Figs 2, 3. The wings of *Atrichobrunettia (Mirousiella) graeca* Ježek et Goutner, 1993 (2) and *Clogmia albipunctata* (Williston, 1893) (3); scales: 0.5 mm.

Cazan et al., 2019b), the family Psychodidae is under-researched in Romania. Firstly, Vaillant & Botoșăneanu (1966) published 23 species from Romania. These records are complemented mainly based on records by Botoșăneanu & Vaillant (1965), as well as Vaillant (1963), (1971–1983), etc. Summarisation was also added in Fauna Europaea by Wagner (2013) with 38 records of non Phlebotominae species of this family. However not all species mentioned in previous papers are summarised here (13 species miss).

Altogether, 53 species are listed in the present checklist of non-Phlebotominae species of family Psychodidae in Romania (Sycoracinae: 2 spp., Trichomyiinae: 1 sp., Psychodinae: 50 spp. (in detail: Mormiini: 2 spp., Paramormiini: 12 spp. Pericomaini: 23 spp., Psychodini: 12 spp., Maruinini: 1 sp.)).

The updated checklist of non-Phlebotominae species of the family Psychodidae of Romania

(sensu Vaillant, 1963; Botoșăneanu & Vaillant, 1965; Vaillant & Botoșăneanu, 1966; Vaillant, 1971–1983; Wagner, 2013)

Family Psychodidae

Subfamily Sycoracinae

Sycorax silacea Haliday in Curtis, 1839

Sycorax similis (Müller, 1927)

Subfamily Trichomyiinae

Trichomyia urbica Haliday in Curtis, 1839

Subfamily Psychodinae

Tribus Mormiini

Subtribus Brunettiina

Atrichobrunettia (Mirousiella) graeca Ježek et Goutner, 1993 *

Subtribus Mormiina

Yomormia banatica (Vaillant, 1974)

Tribus Paramormiini

Subtribus Paramormiina

Clogmia albipunctata (Williston, 1893) *

Jungiella (Jungiella) botosaneanui (Vaillant, 1963)
(larva only)

Jungiella (Jungiella) soleata (Walker, 1856)

Jungiella (Jungiella) valachica (Vaillant, 1963)

Panimerus albifacies (Tonnoir, 1919)

Panimerus notabilis (Eaton, 1893)

Paramormia (Duckhousiella) ustulata (Walker, 1856)

Paramormia (Phyllotelmatoscopus) decipiens (Eaton, 1893)

Peripsychoda auriculata (Haliday in Curtis, 1839)

Subtribus Trichopsychodina

Philosepedon (Philosepedon) carpaticum Vaillant, 1974

Philosepedon (Philosepedon) kalehnum Vaillant, 1974

Philosepedon scutigerum Vaillant, 1963 ? (larva only)

Tribus Pericomaini

Berdeniella bucegica Vaillant, 1976

Berdeniella unispinosa (Tonnoir, 1919)

Clytocerus (Boreoclytocerus) ocellaris (Meigen, 1818)

Parabazarella subneglecta (Tonnoir, 1922)
Pericoma (Botosaneanuiella) attenuata Vaillant, 1978
Pericoma (Pachypericoma) blandula Eaton, 1893
Pericoma (Pericoma) calcilega Feuerborn, 1923
Pericoma (Pericoma) incrustans Vaillant, 1978 (larva only)
Pericoma (Pericoma) motasi Vaillant, 1978
Pericoma (Pericoma) pingarestica Vaillant, 1978
Pneumia bucegiana (Vaillant, 1981)
Pneumia canescens (Meigen, 1804)
Pneumia nubila (Meigen, 1818)
Pneumia palustris (Meigen, 1818)
Pneumia vittata (Tonnoir, 1919)
Saraiella austriana (Vaillant, 1963)
Saraiella carpatica Vaillant, 1981
Saraiella crypta (Vaillant, 1955)
Saraiella parva (Vaillant, 1963)
Tonnoiriella pulchra (Eaton, 1893)
Ulomyia fuliginosa (Meigen, 1818)
Ulomyia ophicornis Vaillant, 1983
Ulomyia rostrata Vaillant, 1983

Tribus Psychodini

Chodopsycha lobata (Tonnoir, 1940)
Feuerborniella obscura (Tonnoir, 1919)
Logima albipennis (Zetterstedt, 1850)
Logima erminea (Eaton, 1893)
Psychoda phalaenoides Linnaeus, 1758
Psychodocha cinerea (Banks, 1894)
Psychodocha gemina (Eaton, 1904)
Psychodula minuta (Banks, 1894)
Psychomora trinodulosa (Tonnoir, 1922)
Tinearina alternata (Say, 1824)
Tinearina lativentris (Berdn, 1952)
Ypsydocha setigera (Tonnoir, 1922)

Tribus Maruinini

Lobulosa transsylvanica (Szabó, 1960)

The new country records are marked by an asterisk. *P. scutigerum* Vaillant, 1963 is known only from the larva. According to Vaillant (who doubts the correctness of the taxon), it could (see the Vaillant's comments in the Lindner's monography 9d, 305 (1974), p. 119) also be a synonym of the species *P. balcanicum* Krek, 1971, *P. mayeri* (Satchell, 1955) or *P. soljani* Krek, 1971, or, according to today's view it could be provisionally included in one of the subgenera

Trichosepedon Krek, 1999 or *Philothreticus* Krek, 1999. Therefore, the species is not even mentioned by Omelková & Ježek (2012).

From 53 species recorded, three are known only based on larvae. One recorded species, *C. albipunctata* appears to be as a dangerous species. This invasive, often synanthropic species may pose a risk for native synanthropic species, rare tree holes species, and also is epidemiological significant as a possible causal agent of various myiasis (e.g. Oboňa & Ježek, 2012; Cazorla-Perfetti, 2019; Martynov et al., 2022; Jaume-Schinkel et al., 2022). From the ecosozological point of view, *A. (M.) graeca*, together with *T. urbica*, *Y. banatica*, *P. (P.) decipiens*, *P. (P.) carpaticum*, *P. (P.) kalehnum*, *B. bucegica*, *P. (B.) attenuata*, *P. (P.) motasi*, *P. bucegiana*, *P. austriana*, *S. carpatica*, *S. crypta*, *S. parva*, *U. ophicornis*, *U. rostrata*, and *L. transsylvanica* are considered to be rare species and may be included in the Romanian red list in the future.

The investigation of non-Phlebotominae Psychodidae in Romania is still far from finished. This argument can be supported by Ježek et al. (2020), who examined Psychodidae fauna in a neighbouring country, Bulgaria, with 99 species.

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